

Localized Carbon Deposition Enables Non-Invasive Trimming of Photonic Integrated Circuits

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Abstract

Photonic integrated circuits (PICs), widely used in optical communications and computing, require precise post-fabrication trimming due to their high sensitivity to fabrication imperfections. Focused ion beam (FIB) carbon deposition offers a promising solution, combining high spatial precision with minimal invasiveness and inherently broad material compatibility. Here, we demonstrate this technique for the first time to enable non-volatile post-fabrication trimming of PICs. To validate this approach, we use asymmetric directional couplers as representative fabrication-sensitive components. Structural characterizations verify the non-invasive nature of the localized carbon deposition, and device measurements show discrete transmission tuning levels of 1.46–16.1 dB with a trimming-induced insertion loss of only 0.3 dB. Furthermore, the optical response remains stable over two months following a brief initial settling phase. These results establish FIB carbon deposition as a robust and broadly applicable PIC trimming technique, empowering optical communications, computing, and beyond to meet rising data demands.

Introduction

A photonic integrated circuit (PIC) is a microchip that brings together multiple photonic components with different functions. Due to the inherent properties of light, such as high speed, low propagation loss, and high parallelism, PICs have been widely explored in applications such as optical communications^{1–4}, quantum computing^{5–7}, and neuromorphic computing^{8–10}. The outstanding performance of PICs in these applications relies on the proper operation of precisely engineered photonic structures, which are often vulnerable to fabrication imperfections. The accumulation of optical response deviations with increasing device count has thus made fabrication imperfections a key obstacle to the further development of PICs. Post-fabrication trimming provides an effective approach to correct such imperfections, offering precise, localized, and flexible control over photonic device performance^{11–13}.

Various post-fabrication trimming techniques have been proposed to address fabrication imperfections, including micro-heaters^{14,15}, electron beam exposure of polymer claddings^{16–18}, and focused ion beam processing^{15,19}. The trimming method based on micro-heaters usually requires continuous heating to maintain the desired tuning states, resulting in significant power consumption and can cause thermal crosstalk. Polymer cladding trimming is a simple and cost-effective method, but it generally cannot guarantee long-term stability. Focused ion beam (FIB) techniques have been widely used in nanofabrication due to their high spatial resolution and mask-free characteristics²⁰. In recent years, silicon ion implantation using FIB has emerged as a promising technique for post-fabrication trimming, offering permanent refractive index changes with low optical loss and excellent stability^{19,21}. However, this approach faces challenges in achieving delicate fine-tuning. The strong refractive index contrast between the amorphous silicon-rich regions and the silicon nitride (SiN) waveguide leads to drastic changes in the field distribution of the guided mode, making nanometer-scale tuning highly exacting and

sometimes unattainable. In addition, the high-energy ion beam can cause structural damage, restricting its applicability primarily to platforms such as silicon and SiN.

FIB deposition of amorphous carbon as a non-invasive trimming technology has great potential for achieving platform-independent fine-tuning. This technique utilizes a focused ion beam to locally decompose precursor gas molecules, enabling precise deposition of diamond-like amorphous carbon^{22–24}. Over the past few decades, the technique has been mainly used for the fabrication of 3D nanostructures^{20,25,26}, though diamond-like amorphous carbon can also be used in anti-reflection coating^{27–29}, protective coatings^{30,31}, and as hard masks for etching^{32,33}. However, its application in post-fabrication trimming of PICs has not yet been explored. Given that FIB is a mature technology with equipment widely available in research facilities and advanced manufacturing laboratories, this presents a valuable opportunity for precise post-fabrication trimming in PICs.

To validate the trimming capability of FIB carbon deposition, we investigated asymmetric directional couplers (A-DCs) as a representative device. A-DCs are widely used for on-chip mode conversion^{34–36} and rely on precise phase matching between selected modes, which occurs when their effective refractive indices (n_{eff}) are equal at a given wavelength. Because of this strong dependence on precise phase matching, A-DCs are sensitive to fabrication imperfections, making them an ideal platform for evaluating post-fabrication trimming techniques.

In this study, we demonstrate FIB carbon deposition as a non-invasive technique with great stability that can be used for high-resolution post-fabrication trimming of PICs. To validate its effectiveness, we employ A-DCs as a sensitive test structure, where trimming allows precise control of device responses. We also quantify the trimming-induced insertion loss, accessible tuning range, and long-term stability, confirming the method's flexibility and robustness for post-fabrication trimming in PICs.

Results

To visualize the trimming process, consider an A-DC composed of a narrow waveguide (width w_0) placed adjacent to a wider waveguide (width w_1), separated by a gap g . Both waveguides share the same height h and sit atop a buried oxide (BOX) layer on a silicon substrate. Trimming begins when a carbon-containing precursor gas is directed toward the narrow waveguide through a gas nozzle, as shown in Fig. 1a. The Ga^+ ion beam induces local decomposition of the precursor gas molecules when exposed to the waveguide, resulting in the accumulation of carbon in the irradiation region with nanometer scale precision (see Supplementary S1 for the actual FIB sample stage diagram). In this study, we chose to deposit carbon on the narrow waveguide to control the n_{eff} of the TE_0 mode for demonstration purposes. Carbon can also be deposited on the wide waveguide to control higher-order modes²¹.

Complementing the schematic, a fabricated A-DC based on the TE_2 mode (see Supplementary S2 for fabrication process) is shown in Fig. 1b. Light is input via a grating coupler and is equally split by a

multimode interferometer. Half of the input light is directed to the output grating coupler (indicated by the white dashed box) and measured by a photodetector. The resulting transmission spectrum is used as the reference for normalization. The first A-DC converts the remaining light from the TE₀ mode to the TE₂ mode. After conversion, the light propagates along the bus waveguide in the TE₂ mode and is converted back to the TE₀ mode by the second A-DC before reaching the output grating coupler. For simplicity, we assume in this study that the measured insertion loss is dominated by the mode conversions.

Building on the device structure, we simulated the mode conversion behavior of A-DCs based on the TE₁ and TE₂ modes, using parameters of $w_0 = 1200$ nm, $g = 300$ nm, and $h = 335$ nm. By adjusting the bus waveguide width, an insertion loss of 0.055 dB for the TE₁ mode and 0.045 dB for the TE₂ mode is achieved for the A-DC at 1550 nm, as shown in Fig. 1c and 1f. The insets show that the TE₀ mode light in the narrow waveguide is converted into the higher-order mode light in the wide waveguide. Figure 1d and 1g exhibit the transmission of the A-DCs at a wavelength of 1550 nm under different w_1 values, where the highest transmission appears at $w_1 = 2550$ nm and 3900 nm, respectively. These structures were then fabricated for verification. Experimentally, there was only minimal deviation from the expected waveguide widths, mainly owing to the shrinkage of resist during the hot plate baking process. We observe the measured insertion losses to be 0.4 dB and 0.5 dB with waveguide widths of 2475 nm and 3750 nm for TE₁ and TE₂ modes, in that order. In addition, the observed insertion losses of 2.7 dB and 7.4 dB for the TE₁ and TE₂ modes at $w_1 = 2550$ nm and 3900 nm, respectively, further highlight the necessity of a wide tuning range for mode control.

In the experiment, the w_1 value that achieved the highest transmission was slightly lower than the simulation results for the two modes. This is because resist shrinkage has a greater influence on the n_{eff} of the TE₀ mode in the narrow waveguide, which can be compensated by depositing carbon. Figure 2a shows the n_{eff} of the TE₀ mode can be flexibly controlled by changing the carbon geometry. The refractive index n and extinction coefficient k of the carbon in our simulation models are 2.48 and 0.019, respectively³⁷. Due to its small geometric dimensions and moderate refractive index, the deposited carbon has a negligible effect on the field distribution of the TE₀ mode, as shown in Fig. 2b. To study the effect of carbon on the optical response of A-DCs, we reduce w_0 from 1200 nm to 1150 nm while keeping w_1 unchanged, thereby breaking the phase-matching conditions. As shown in Fig. 2c and 2d, after placing the carbon model on the narrow waveguide, the insertion loss decreases from approximately 5 dB to 0.24 dB (TE₁ mode) and 0.33 dB (TE₂ mode).

The trimming-induced insertion losses are approximately 0.2 dB for the TE₁-mode A-DCs and 0.24 dB for the TE₂-mode A-DCs, which are slightly higher than those induced by silicon ion implantation¹⁹ or polymer-based trimming¹⁸, as the deposited carbon is not perfectly lossless at 1550 nm. These values, however, remain lower than those typically reported for germanium ion implantation (~ 3 dB for 100 μm ³⁸). For trimming applications, a small k has only a minimal impact on the overall insertion loss. As

shown in Fig. 2e, when the k value gradually increases from 0 to 0.1, the insertion loss of the TE₁-mode A-DC increases from 0.035 dB to 1.08 dB. This can be generalized as an approximation: for every 0.01 increase in the k value here, the insertion loss increases by approximately 0.1 dB. Since the output of the bar port is almost the same in Fig. 2f, the increased insertion loss is mainly caused by the increase in light absorption. The TE₂ mode-based A-DC also exhibits the same trend, but with an insertion loss that increases by approximately 0.13 dB for every 0.01 increase in the k value. This is mainly owed to the crossover length of the TE₂ mode, 110 μm , which is longer than the 90 μm in the TE₁ mode.

To explore the impact of carbon deposition at the nanoscale, electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) spectra were first used to determine the bandgaps of the SiN waveguide (5.25 eV) and the deposited carbon (3.9 eV), the latter corresponding to diamond-like carbon³⁹. As a complementary technique, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) imaging with energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis was used to examine the cross-section of the cut narrow waveguide and reveal how the carbon integrates with the underlying structure. Figure 3a and 3b show the elemental mapping of the waveguide after carbon deposition. In the elemental maps of carbon and gallium, we observe an increase in brightness in the local area above the waveguide, indicating that the deposited layer has a mixture of gallium and carbon⁴⁰. The gallium originates from the Ga⁺ ion beam used during the FIB-assisted carbon deposition. Importantly, gallium signal is confined to the deposited layer and absent from the underlying SiN waveguide. This is consistent with the use of a low probe current (20 pA) at 30 kV acceleration voltage, conditions that favor surface-assisted carbon deposition rather than gallium implantation. Under these parameters, the interaction volume of Ga⁺ ions is minimal relative to the waveguide core, keeping the process firmly in the deposition regime.

This is further supported by the line scan profile in Fig. 3c, showing a localized increase in both carbon and gallium above the waveguide. According to the elemental maps, the carbon deposition is non-invasive and limited to the designated area, with no significant changes in elemental composition detected in the underlying SiN. Furthermore, the plasmon map in Fig. 3d and the corresponding high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) micrograph in Fig. 3e together corroborate this conclusion: the plasmon map reveals negligible variations in the plasmon energy and intensity after carbon deposition, suggesting that the collective electronic response of the material remains unchanged. Combined with the HAADF micrograph, these observations confirm that the deposition is confined to this region and no significant structural alterations are detectable within the resolution limits of this method. Therefore, this method is expected to be compatible with different platforms without requiring any platform-specific modifications.

Since the carbon is not completely lossless, we prepared simple Mach-Zehnder interferometers (MZIs) to evaluate the introduced insertion loss. Carbon was deposited on one arm of the MZIs with a fixed length of 20 μm (see Supplementary S3 for MZI images). The measured insertion loss is approximately 0.14 dB, comparable to 0.125 dB obtained from simulations. Compared to a standalone waveguide, the loss caused by trimming in A-DCs is approximately half. The supermodes formed in the coupling region

distribute the optical power between the two waveguides, thereby reducing the proportion of the light interacting with the deposited carbon. Hence, the deposited carbon introduces only 0.3 dB loss to the TE₁-mode A-DCs (90 μm trimmed length). If a shorter structure is used and the trimming length is reduced, the introduced loss becomes almost negligible.

With both the elemental distribution and optical loss confirmed, attention turns to the trimmed region within the A-DC structures. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of the TE₁-mode A-DC after carbon deposition is presented in Fig. 4a. A dimmer line can be observed on the narrow waveguide, formed by carbon deposition, which increases the n_{eff} value of the TE₀ mode to meet the phase-matching conditions. The length of the deposited carbon is designed to match the crossover length of the A-DC, ensuring efficient mode conversion across the entire coupling region. After carbon deposition, the measured insertion loss of the A-DC is reduced from 1.81 dB to 0.36 dB, as shown in Fig. 4b. To corroborate the experimental results, we conducted simulations, and the results in Fig. 4c exhibit good agreement with measurement results, further validating the effectiveness of carbon deposition in controlling the mode conversion. In the SEM image of the TE₂-mode A-DC after carbon deposition (Fig. 4d), we observe that the carbon is not perfectly centered in the narrow waveguide, however, according to our simulation results even when the center position offset reaches ± 100 nm, there is almost no influence on the n_{eff} of the TE₀ mode.

Figure 4 SEM image of A-DCs after carbon deposition and the corresponding transmission spectra. a SEM image of the trimmed A-DC for TE₁ mode. **b** Measured transmission spectra of the TE₁-mode A-DC. **c** simulation results used to study the measurement results. In this model, $w_0 = 1155$ nm, $w_1 = 2510$ nm, $h = 340$ nm, and $g = 300$ nm. The major and minor axis lengths of the carbon structure are 120 nm and 60 nm, respectively. **d** SEM image of the TE₂-mode device. **e** Measured transmission spectra of the TE₂-mode A-DC. **f** Simulation results for studying the measured spectra. In this model, $w_0 = 1155$ nm, $w_1 = 3870$ nm, $h = 340$ nm, and $g = 280$ nm. The major and minor axis lengths are 100 nm and 60 nm, respectively

Figure 4e shows a significant transmission improvement, where the insertion loss at approximately 1550 nm decreased from 4.5 dB to 0.82 dB after trimming. This result is in close agreement with the simulated data presented in Fig. 4f. Herein we discuss carbon deposition using TE₁ and TE₂ modes as examples, but it can be extended to higher-order modes, demonstrating excellent versatility.

Carbon deposition also provides wide tuning capability, ensuring compatibility with a broad range of initial waveguide conditions, as shown in Fig. 5a. Here, the initial insertion losses of the A-DCs to be trimmed are gradually increased from 1.8 dB to 17.8 dB. For the TE₁-mode A-DCs at $w_1 = 2525$ nm (marked as 1), the improvement in the insertion loss is as fine as 1.46 dB, from 1.83 dB to 0.37 dB, confirming the feasibility of this method for fine-tuning. For the TE₂-mode A-DCs at $w_1 = 3950$ nm (marked as 6), the improvement in the insertion loss can reach as high as 16.1 dB, from 17.8 dB to 1.7 dB.

To evaluate the long-term stability of this non-volatile post-fabrication trimming method, we measured the transmission of the TE₁-mode A-DC at different time points. As shown in Fig. 5b, the transmission slightly decreases during the first two weeks and then stabilizes. The minor change in transmission observed within the first two weeks is likely attributed to stress relaxation or gradual structural stabilization of the deposited carbon, a process can be accelerated by thermal annealing. To verify this hypothesis, a device was prepared and annealed at 200 °C, followed by measurement at different time intervals. The annealing temperature was selected because heating beyond approximately 300 °C causes the deposited carbon to transition from diamond-like carbon to graphite-like carbon^{23,41}. The optical response of the device tended to stabilize after approximately 30 minutes of annealing treatment (see Supplementary 4). Based on the results, the chip containing the TE₂-mode A-DC was placed on a hot plate at 200 °C for 30 minutes. As shown in Fig. 5c, the transmission exhibited a slight decrease after heating, but it remains stable over the following weeks after the heat treatment, indicating great stability.

Due to its mask-free nature, the FIB-based carbon deposition demonstrates exceptional flexibility in the post-fabrication trimming. This trimming method combined with A-DCs can be applied to photonic crossbar arrays^{9,42,43}, which are commonly used to perform matrix-vector multiplication (MVM) operations to accelerate artificial intelligence tasks. As shown in Fig. 6a, the A-DCs (indicated by a white dashed box) can be added before the output grating coupler to combine the output light of two small 9×2 crossbar arrays, which is equivalent to performing an addition operation.

Figure 6b shows an image of the A-DC in the very same crossbar configuration. For directional couplers based on the TE₀ mode, we observe that after combination, the output power of each input is reduced by 3 dB due to the 50:50 power splitting. Because the orthogonal modes (e.g., TE₀ and TE₁ modes) are independent, when using an A-DC based on mode-division multiplexing (MDM) technology for combination, the loss here can be approximated as the insertion loss, which is much lower than 3 dB after carbon deposition. Figure 6c shows a comparison of transmitted light before and after carbon deposition. The insertion loss for the conversion from the TE₀ mode to TE₁ mode decreases from approximately 3 dB to 0.5 dB after trimming, ensuring efficient combination.

Discussion

We present a trimming method for PICs based on FIB carbon deposition, which is non-invasive, non-volatile, low-loss, and highly stable. As a representative case, we demonstrate its application in post-fabrication tuning of A-DCs, achieving insertion losses as low as 0.36 dB after trimming and showcasing discrete trimming levels ranging from ~ 1.5 dB to 16.1 dB. These results validate the method's effectiveness on a fabrication-sensitive component, while its combined advantages render it broadly applicable well beyond A-DCs. For a trimming length of ~ 100 μm, the carbon-induced loss is only ~ 0.3 dB, demonstrating the minimal optical penalty associated with this technique. The trimmed devices also maintain stable performance over a period exceeding two months, confirming the long-term reliability of

the method. Compared with thermal tuning, this approach consumes no continuous power and requires no local heaters, enabling more compact and densely integrated devices. It also circumvents the limitations of ion implantation: while this technique offers high precision and excellent long-term stability, its most common form, Ge ion implantation, often results in significant absorption loss and waveguide core damage; in contrast, our method incurs only minimal insertion loss and fully preserves core integrity. These features make the method well suited for a wide range of PIC applications demanding precise optical control, such as MDM components for expanding processing capacity and large-scale photonic accelerators requiring low-loss signal combination.

Crucially, elemental mapping and EELS plasmon map confirm its non-invasive nature, underpinning broad compatibility across diverse material platforms. Although Ga ions are detected in the STEM EDS analysis, our EELS measurements show that the deposited carbon exhibits a bandgap of 3.9 eV, well within the accepted range for diamond-like amorphous carbon. This in turn, indicates that Ga content remains below levels that would compromise optical performance, as further supported by the transmission spectra of photonic devices after carbon deposition. Building on these advantages, FIB carbon deposition offers a mask-free solution for post-fabrication tuning in both current silicon-based platforms and emerging material systems. As such, this method provides a practical and forward-compatible pathway toward large-scale, energy-efficient, and yield-enhancing photonic integration across a wide spectrum of applications from high-density interconnects to next-generation optical computing systems.

Methods

Focused Ion Beam-Induced Carbon Deposition on SiN

Carbon deposition on SiN substrates was performed using a ZEISS Crossbeam 540 FIB/SEM system equipped with a multi-channel Gas Injection System (GIS). Samples were mounted onto the stage and introduced into the chamber, where the stage was tilted to 54° to align the sample surface normal to the FIB column.

Once thermal and vacuum equilibrium was achieved, a carbon precursor gas was introduced via the GIS. Using a FIB probe current of 20 pA at 30 kV, a carbon line of a specified length was deposited directly on top of the waveguides. The ion beam and GIS were activated simultaneously, and the deposition dose was calibrated to achieve a nominal carbon thickness of ~ 50 nm.

STEM analysis of the trimmed SiN waveguides

Post-trimming analysis of the SiN waveguides was performed using a Thermo Fisher Scientific FEI Themis 300 G3 Titan scanning/transmission electron microscope (S/TEM), operated at 300/60 kV. Samples were prepared in cross-sectional orientation using the FIB technique on a ZEISS Crossbeam 540 FIB/SEM system. The specimens were thinned to electron transparency for imaging. Elemental

mapping was conducted in STEM mode using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). To investigate bandgap variations in the trimmed waveguides, electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) was performed in monochromated STEM mode at 60 kV. The analysis focused on the low-loss region of the EELS spectrum, which contains information about interband transitions and plasmon excitations that are sensitive to changes in the electronic structure and optical bandgap.

Declarations

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: R. X., S. T. and R. R. S., Simulation: R. X., L. M. and L. M., Sample fabrication: R. X., Z. T., A. V. and S. T., Data acquisition and analysis: R. X., Z. T., Z. Z, R. P., X. M., Q. Z and F. B. P., Visualization: R.X., J. B., J. R., and J. D., Writing: All authors, Supervision: W. H. P. P., S. T., R. R. S., and H. B.

Competing interests.

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Figures

Figure 1

Schematic diagram of a trimmed A-DC using carbon deposition, and the transmission response of the untrimmed A-DCs. **a** Schematic of a trimmed A-DC by carbon deposition. **b** Images of a fabricated A-DC for mode conversion between TE_0 and TE_2 modes. **c** Simulated transmission spectrum and intensity distribution of the TE_1 -mode A-DC. **d, e** Simulated and measured transmission of the TE_1 -mode A-DCs

with increasing w_1 . The difference between the simulation results and the measurement results is due to fabrication errors in the width of the waveguides. **f** Simulated transmission spectrum and intensity distribution of the TE₂-mode A-DC. **g, h** Simulated and measured transmission of the TE₂-mode A-DCs with increasing w_1 .

Figure 2

Simulation results of asymmetric directional couplers before and after carbon deposition. **a** Effective refractive index of the TE₀ mode varies with the major axis length of carbon. When $w_0 = 1150$ nm and major axis length = 160 nm, the n_{eff} of the TE₀ mode is equal to the n_{eff} at $w_0=1200$ nm. **b** Intensity distribution of a 1200 nm-wide waveguide, an 1150 nm-wide waveguide, and an 1150 nm-wide waveguide with carbon deposition. The carbon is elliptical with major axis and minor axis lengths of 160 nm and 60 nm. The n and k of the deposited carbon are 2.48 and 0.019³⁷, respectively. Transmission spectra of A-DC with 1150 nm-wide waveguide before and after depositing carbon for **c** TE₁ mode and **d** TE₂ mode. **e** and **f** When the k of the deposited carbon is assumed to vary from 0 to 0.1, the transmission spectra of the A-DC based on the TE₁ mode. **g** and **h** Assuming that the k of the deposited carbon varies from 0 to 0.1, the transmission spectra of the A-DC based on the TE₂ mode.

Figure 3

Transmission electron microscope study of the deposited carbon. **a** Cross-section of the cut waveguide with carbon deposition. **b** STEM EDS elemental mapping of the waveguide. **c** Line scan profile of the deposited carbon indicated using a red dashed line in the cross-section image. **d, e** Plasmon map and HAADF micrograph of the cross-sectional region near the deposited carbon.

Figure 4

SEM image of A-DCs after carbon deposition and the corresponding transmission spectra. **a** SEM image of the trimmed A-DC for TE₁ mode. **b** Measured transmission spectra of the TE₁-mode A-DC. **c** simulation results used to study the measurement results. In this model, $w_0 = 1155$ nm, $w_1 = 2510$ nm, $h = 340$ nm, and $g = 300$ nm. The major and minor axis lengths of the carbon structure are 120 nm and 60 nm, respectively. **d** SEM image of the TE₂-mode device. **e** Measured transmission spectra of the TE₂-mode A-DC. **f** Simulation results for studying the measured spectra. In this model, $w_0 = 1155$ nm, $w_1 = 3870$ nm, $h = 340$ nm, and $g = 280$ nm. The major and minor axis lengths are 100 nm and 60 nm, respectively

Figure 5

Transmission of A-DCs at 1550 nm with different initial insertion losses and stability of the optical response of the trimmed A-DCs over time. **a** Devices 1–3 are TE₁-mode A-DCs with $w_1 = 2525$ nm, 2550 nm, and 2575 nm, respectively. Device 4–6 are TE₂-mode A-DCs with $w_1 = 3900$ nm, 3925 nm, 3950 nm, respectively. The initial insertion losses of these devices vary from 1.8 dB to 17.8 dB. A single carbon deposition can improve insertion loss by up to 16.1 dB. **b** Transmission at 1550 nm for the TE₁-mode A-DC over time. The decrease in transmission stops after the second week, and the transmission remains stable for at least 6 weeks thereafter. The final insertion loss is approximately 0.75 dB. **c** Transmission of the A-DC based on the TE₂ mode at 1550 nm over time. The device was annealed on a hot plate at 200°C for 30 minutes. After annealing, the transmission decreases slightly and remains stable for at least 4 weeks thereafter. All the samples in this study were stored in ambient air without any special treatment.

Figure 6

Flexible post-fabrication trimming using carbon deposition in a photonic crossbar array. **a** An image of the fabricated photonic crossbar array based on the wavelength-division multiplexing and MDM techniques. **b** Schematic of the application of MDM in the photonic crossbar array. **c** Sum of the output powers from the two constituent arrays before and after carbon deposition. Since the TE₀ mode light from array 1 experiences almost no loss when passing through the A-DC, its output power here is used as a normalized reference.

Supplementary Files

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